

Bullying in Retailing: A Study of Non Branded Readymade Garment Sector

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ABSTRACT

Bullying is a process in which people face criticism continuously in public and private, which humiliates that person. It has a detrimental impact on their performance, business, family, personal life and on their health also. The purpose of this paper is to address the problems faced by retailers of readymade garments who deal in non-branded clothes with the logo of original brand names. The research method used in this study is interview i.e. face to face and telephonic interview, in which 20 retailers selected through simple random sampling and shopkeepers express their views and opinions that what types of problems they are facing due to bullying and their consequences. Apart from this, retailers also give some suggestions to cope up with this situation.

Keywords-- Bullying, Criticism, Detrimental, Performance, Retailers

The first person, who investigated on the given topic is Brodsky, "The harassed worker", a book written by him in 1976, in which he described some stories about people who faced the problem of bullying in different workplaces. These people had suffered from long term harassment from their colleagues and superior, Einarsen, S, Matthiesen, S, (2010). Well, there is no universally accepted formal definition of workplace bullying, whereas some researchers put questions whether a particular definition is possible because of its complexity and different forms however, some researchers try to define it:

Bullying in the workplace can be defined by Einarsen and Matthiesen (2010) is that: "One or more employees systematically and over a long period of time perceiving to be on the receiving end of direct or indirect aggression in the workplace, in a situation in which the person(s) exposed to the treatment has difficulty in defending themselves against this treatment. Another Researcher Gary and Ruth Namie, (2014), define workplace bullying as "Repeated, health-harming mistreatment, verbal abuse, or conduct which is threatening, humiliating, intimidating, or sabotage that interferes with work or some combination of the three." Therefore, the research will help for collecting an information from retailers of readymade garments (deals in non-branded clothes), that how bullying affects the readymade industry.

I. INTRODUCTION

Individuals, who finds enjoyment in the activity that relates to the repeated aggressive behavior intended to hurt another individual physically, mentally or emotionally is called bullying. Bullying is a sub-part of aggressive behavior which is further divided into three categories such as hostile intent, imbalance of power and repetition over a period of time, Burger, Christoph; Strohmeier, Dagmar; Sporber, Nina, Bauman, Sheri; Rigby, Ken, (2015). The term bullying can also be defined as the process in which people face constant criticism and personal abuse in public and private, which humiliates and demeans that person, Adams, A, (1992). Behavior used to assert such domination may include physical attack or force, verbal harassment, or threat, and such acts may be directed repeatedly toward particular targets. A bullying culture develops in any context in which people interact with each other which include school, family, the workplace, the home and neighborhoods, Elizabeth Bennett, (2006). Bullying is divided into four basic types of abuse i.e. psychological (sometimes called emotional or rational), verbal, physical and cyber, Brank, Eve M; Hoetger, Logi A, Hazen, Katherine P, (2012). The main motive behind this research is to get information about bullying behind the retailers.

II. RESEARCH OBJECTIVE

The primary objective of this research is to find problems faced by shopkeepers of readymade garments who deal in duplicacy of clothes i.e. first and second copy of branded clothes due to bullying.

III. RESEARCH QUESTIONS

- 1). How bullying affects retailers personal and business life?
- 2). To investigate the consequences of bullying by companies who harassed these retailers.
- 3). How government would help these retailers to prevent them from bullying?

IV. LITERATURE REVIEW

Bloom (2010) defined that stress is the main reason which put an adverse effect on the performance of work in organizations. The employees play a paramount role in delivering the services to customers and employers, and most of those times employees are experiencing stressful environment. So, due to this stressful environment, they have to suffer lots of problems like depression, traumatic conditions and so on.

Abdelrazek and Elhosany (2016) have conducted their research on nursing staff in which researchers analyzed that nursing staff were dominated by emotional abuse. During this research, the behaviors of nurses have been noted about their leadership qualities and creative abilities. Hence, just because of the emotional abuses, the overall developments of nurses lead to be low.

V. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Methodology is the process in which certain procedures or techniques used to identify select, process and analyze information about a topic (research problem). Methodology is the systematic, theoretical analysis of the methods that applied to a field of study. In this study, qualitative research was used to collect primary data and information to answer the research question by survey method. Survey can be further divided into two sub-parts: questionnaire and interviews. In this research, data is collected through personal interviews and telephonic interviews.

VI. SAMPLE SIZE

In this study, sample size was taken of 20 shopkeepers from Dhuri city in Sangrur district, Punjab. There are near about 60 shops in this city. In this, interview was conducted to collect information from retailers who are selling first and second copy of branded clothes about the consequences of bullying on them. Data is collected in the form of interview. They described the problems and suggestion.

VII. PROBLEMS FACED BY RETAILERS

There are several problems faced by small shopkeeper who are dealing in duplicacy of branded clothes such as Nike, Adidas, Puma, Superdry, Versace, and Gucci and so on. The major problem faced by them is when the contractors who take the contract from big branded companies to raid on the small shopkeepers. According to the shopkeepers, they have no fault because if factories would not manufacture and sell these type of clothes, then

how they would sale it, which is a case of bullying on these retailers. The problems faced by them due to this bullying are as follow:

1. There is always threat in the minds of retailers that when the employees of the company raid over the shops. As a result, of this there would be a drastic change in their life. Since, it gives birth to many health and mental issues such as depression, hypertension, cardiovascular and so many other diseases which relates to stress.
2. Retailers also said that while doing this kind of work, they are not doing any kind of illegal activity; as if they are doing then it should be completely banned. So, when there is a raid on their shop, retailers get affected because they have good reputation in the city and other people have no knowledge about this and think that shopkeeper might be doing any kind of illegal business. That's why police raid over this shop.
3. A more problem faced by them is that when this kind of activity is done, they get affected financially. As the employees of company take their stock in bulk amount from their shops. Apart from this, they also grab a huge amount of money from them and start a legal case against them for this and they have to close their shops to attend the hearings in the court. Hence, due to all of this not only the retailers but their families also suffered because of rise in expenses and lower in income.
4. Moreover, during the peak of their season, sometimes shopkeepers have to remain closed their shops when they find that there are more chances of raid as the news of their presence in the market. Hence, retailers have to suffer a lot in both financial and personal level.

IX. SUGGESTIONS GIVEN BY RETAILERS

1. Retailers want that in India like other developed countries, readymade market would mostly cover by branded clothes i.e. some local brands would be there so those people who cannot afford expensive brands buy local brand.
2. They said that if owners of branded clothes want that duplicacy will be completely abolished from Indian market then first they close the big factories those are manufacturing and selling these types of clothes as compare to harassing small retailers.
3. An another suggestion given by them is that government should protect them because we pay all taxes and make some stringent laws so that without any fear like other business men they can run their business.

4. Shopkeepers suggested that factories should make superior quality of clothes of local brand so consumers will not face any kind of problem.

X. CONCLUSION

Overall, the investigation about bullying on the retailers found that most of the small shopkeepers are very upset and frustrated from this problem as all the time they have to do their work in fear and faces huge financial losses due to this problem. Almost, every shopkeeper wants that they do their work without any fear and lead normal life. They want government should cease these factories which are dealing in first and second copy of branded clothes. So, they will make some new local branded clothes with good quality and affordable range. Due to which, there would be no adverse effect on their personal and business life and their problems will solved.

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